

amongst public officials as it circumscribes merit in the area of manpower procurement and promotion. The study concludes that for Nigerian public service to achieve its mandate of facilitating development, there is need for the government to reappraise the implementation of the federal character principles through the enforcement of merit, anchored on public service reform initiatives that can galvanize human capacity and governmental institutions for sustainable development.

Keywords: Federal character principle, administrative effectiveness, development, public service

Introduction

The Federal Character Principle in Nigeria aims to ensure equitable representation in public service, promoting integration, national unity, and reducing ethnic dominance. The principle was introduced in the 1979 Constitution, it mandates that government appointments should reflect Nigeria's diverse demographics. However, its implementation has faced criticisms for fostering nepotism and inefficiency, as recruitment often prioritizes ethnic affiliation over merit. This has led to increased ethno-regional tensions and questions about administrative effectiveness, complicating nation-building efforts. Despite its intentions, the principle has sometimes exacerbated divisions rather than mitigate them. Plural and sharply divided societies all over the world attempt to manage their diversities and divisive tendencies through one or combination of policy alternatives in the organization and management of their public services for performance; and Nigeria is not an exception (Ayoade, 2000; Abdullah, 2007). Often times, these policy alternatives turn out to be delicate arrangements; but when carefully conceived, crafted and practiced, it provides opportunity for center-seeking and center-fleeing forces to interact peacefully and co-habit on agreed terms. One of such policy alternatives adopted for the management of the public service in Nigeria for even representation is the federal character principle, which "was borne out of the need to ensure even spread of government appointment, in all the regions, states and local government councils in the

country" (Nzeshi, 2012). This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Bendrix (2023) advocated for policies that are redistributive, as they posit that "policies that are redistributive in nature have become essential components, which are strategically used for the reduction of inequality and promotion of sustainable development in the society".

Nigeria is a federal society comprising 36 states structure, with a population of more than 150 million people and has more than 250 ethnic groups, which necessitate an arrangement that could accommodate people from the different segments of the country in the public bureaucracy (Gberevbie, 2012). The notion of federal character presupposes the existence of a federal society. However, as a federal state, Nigeria was faced with the challenge of how to imbibe the principle of federalism in practice. As a result, the quota system was introduced into the Nigerian public service in 1958 by the government "to ensure equitable representation of the various groups in the country" (Tonwe and Oghator, 2009). To further consolidate on the gains of the quota system, the Federal Military Government of Generals Murtala Mohammed and Olusegun Obasanjo in the drafting and approval of the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria during the transition to civilian rule (1976-79) introduced into the Nigerian political and administrative landscapes the principle of federal character.

Federal character principle sought to give "opportunities in education and employment, usually at the point of entry, to disadvantaged groups and areas to enable them compete and catch up with more advanced areas and sectors of the nation". In comparing the practice of quota system with that of the federal character principle, the latter demands (far more) than the former in the sense that "it switches emphasis from opportunities to privileges and benefits." It was argued that federal character principle is a legal weapon put in place to regulate appointments, promotions, security of tenure and severance in every

government department. The reference to the phrase "disadvantaged groups" in the area of educational opportunities means that "special consideration should be given to candidates from the Northern provinces and other areas where educational facilities were more backward than elsewhere". The awkward application of the federal character principle tends to pose challenges to administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service through the circumscription of merit. Such practice of the principle of federal character in personnel procurement without due regard for merit is more likely to mire efforts at sustainable development in a society.

The formal adoption of the federal system in Nigeria, which came into existence with the introduction of the Littleton constitution of 1954, signaled the need for representative bureaucracy that could address the problem in the composition of the federal public service anchored on effective service delivery (Ayoade, 2000; Ikelegbe, 2004). Public service or administrative effectiveness requires a blend of theory with practice. Accordingly, Max Weber (1864-1920), showed the way forward on how to achieve organizational effectiveness through the theory of ideal bureaucracy; and it is doubtful if any modern human organization, whether in public and private sector can function adequately without adhering to the principle of rationality in employee procurement and rewards as postulated by Max Weber (Anyebe, 2004).

The features of the Weberian (legal-rational) model are: hierarchy which implies structure; promotion based on professional merit; skills as guide for recruitment; the development of career service; reliance on and use of rules and regulations that are scientific; impersonality of relationships among career professionals and their clientele in the bureaucracy, specialization along functional lines; authority and responsibility; and proper documentation or record-keeping in a formal organizational or nation (Anyebe, 2004; Henry, 2007).

Arising from the above, the questions that come to mind are: how has the public service adapted to the Weber's bureaucratic model of rational legal authority for administrative effectiveness in Nigeria? As a federal state, how has the principle of federal character in the procurement and promotion of employees helped to bring into the public service the required competent workforce for enhanced performance? What are the merits and demerits of the introduction and the current implementation of the federal character principle in the Nigerian public service for sustainable development? These questions underline the authors attempt at interrogating the utility and viability of the application of federal character principle in the nation's quest for achieving administrative effectiveness for sustainable development. The study is limited to Federal character principles in Nigeria, impact and challenges. It focuses on the Federal civil service from 2019-2024.

Problems associated with federal character principles in Nigeria

The adoption of Federal character in principles in Nigeria was aimed at addressing the problems of marginalization and inequality in governance and appointment into civil service. The idea was good, however, it failed to yield desired results as major ethnic groups keep dominating political positions in the country including the civil service. Poor implementation of the policy due to manipulation and exclusion of the minority from federal civil service. This research is undertaken with a view of addressing these mirages of problems. The research thus became significant because it would enable members of the public to understand the challenges and impact of implementing federal character principles in Nigeria, and would also enable policy makers to make informed decisions that would ensure strict implementation of Federal character principles. Moreso it would

serve as a source of materials for those who might want to embark on similar study.

Literature Review

Federal character and administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service

The federal character principle which made its debut in-to the Nigerian political and public administrative landscape through the drafting and adoption of the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria appeared to be a normative expression of the historical belief of Nigerians in equal access to and participation in the political and administrative affairs of the country in the area of policy formulation and implementation. To support the above view, Alubo (2003) point out that the lack of representation in policy making and implementation by some segments of the Nigerian society in the past has denied them the opportunities for education and economic advancement. Oaikhena (2023) observed that “public policy occurs when individuals or groups respond to real or perceived environmental conditions”.

In order to drive the implementation of the federal character principle, the Federal Character Commission (FCC) was established by decree 34 of 1996, and the powers of the commission was summarized by Mustapha (2007) to include: working out formula for sharing posts and services; compliance monitoring; enforcement of compliance through legal actions; demanding and reviewing data on staffing; and institutional investigations. The FCC is a commission under the presidency, its members are appointed by the president, but subject to the ratification of the Nigerian Senate. To ensure equity in representation, the law establishing the commission states that, the executive chairman and secretary are to be appointed in such a way that if the chairman comes from the North, the secretary must be chosen from the South and vice versa. However, Nzeshi

(2012) argues that "since its establishment, the Federal Character Commission has been headed mostly by Northerners." To properly implement the federal character principle, a bill was sent to the Nigerian National Assembly for amendment to enable FCC effectively enforce the principles of equity and fairness, and also enable public officers to comply with rules and regulations issued by the commission" (Nzeshi, 2012). The implication of the request to amend the FCC act shows that the principle and the structure put in place to enforce its implementation is not totally effective as envisaged by the government, and this is amply corroborated by Nzeshi (2012) submission that "the inefficiency of the FCC to effectively enforce its mandate as a government watchdog in identifying and addressing inequality is increasingly worrisome." Meanwhile the current chairman of the Federal Character Commission (FCC) in Nigeria is Dr. Muheeba Farida Dankaka (OON). She was appointed as the Executive Chairman of the FCC by President Muhammadu Buhari on April 28, 2020. She still occupies the position till date-September,2024.

In the same vein, Ekeh (1989) contends that "its most radical and damaging application has been in the bureaucracies and public services of the federation. As permanent secretaries have been kicked around, removed and sometimes dismissed." He observed further that the application of the FC principle "has invaded the integrity and standards of public bureaucracy and other governmental bodies that normally require safeguards from the ravages of politics. "Furthermore, the negative effects of federal character on the public sector performance in Nigeria can be gleaned from the work of Forrest (1993), where he argues that the implementation of the principle of federal character in the public service "not only led to poor appointments but also enhanced mediocrity rather than merit." To promote administrative effectiveness for performance in the Nigerian public service, Utomi (2005) observed that "we need to engage

on the issues of competence, commitment, conflict of interest and career certainty. From there come both threats to the effectiveness of the civil service and opportunities for the service to be the anchor of a Nigerian renaissance.

The contributions of a foremost scholar and practitioner in Nigerian public administration, Adamolekun (2008) to this discourse were more probing, when he asserts thus: *“Has the federal character (FC) principle promoted or retarded national loyalty and stability? Or has the area or ethnic region of a person become the key factor in determining his quality as an individual?”* He argues further that “only a critical assessment of years of implementing the FC principle, would help determine the desirable way forward.” It is quite relieving that he answered the above questions in a related discussion thus: The “federal character” principle that was introduced as Nigeria's path to achieving “representative bureaucracy” was morphed into the bad practice of politicization. Capacity development programmes for public servants that were a major concern during the immediate pre and post-independence years was progressively neglected notwithstanding the strong case made for it in the Udoji report 1974 (Adamolekun, 2007).

It is very clear from the above submission, why administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service for sustainable development may continue to be a mirage. Contributing to the debate on public sector ineffectiveness, Suleiman (2009) contends that “poor capacity of the majority of civil servants, sometimes to the point of illiteracy” arising from the application of the FC is one of the reasons for poor performance of the Nigerian public service. The views of Suleiman (2009) and Adamolekun (2009) goes to support the argument that the neglect of capacity development programmes for public servants and the implementation of the FC offer a credible explanation on the ineffectiveness of the Nigerian public bureaucracy for sustainable development in Nigeria. Also, Tonwe

and Oghator (2009) submit that “federal character allows ethno-regional patrons and their clients to exploit and mismanage state resources without contributing to any meaningful development.” As noted by Ojo (2009), “there is no greater inequality than the equal treatment of unequal.” The FC policy as practiced in Nigeria is elitist and class biased, additionally, it leads to a blurring of the boundary between the pursuits of meritocracy and ethnic balancing, thereby creating inadvertently a multiple system of citizenship in the polity.

In addition, the principle and its application have brought about the unintended effect of creating situations of 'elimination by substitution' which makes it counter-productive. This it does through discrimination in appointment and promotion. The principle attempts to achieve equality of all states, whereas states are not equal in population, and size of the pool of candidates for appointment (Ojo, 2009; Tonwe and Oghator, 2009).

According to Ayoade (2009), equality of states in the implementation of the FC principle as enshrined in the Nigerian constitution means "that the North was represented in the ratio 19:17 (52.8 percent) of public posts." He posits that "this situation is further complicated by the fact that arithmetical justice does not necessarily translate to socio-political justice. A representative bureaucracy does not necessarily translate into power equality for the members” (cited in Ojo, 2009: v). Every administration has its own policy goals (Oaikhena,2023).

Viewed from the foregoing submissions, the federal character principle presents an ambiguous and deceitful recipe for equity and unity in a federal society like Nigeria. Supporting the importance of merit as strategy for manpower procurement in the nation's quest for administrative effectiveness and enhanced performance for sustainable development. Soludo (2012) argued that the emergence of a merit driven culture is, therefore, a key outcome of Vision 20:20:20 and an area of immediate policy focus. To this end, a comprehensive review of ethnic balancing

measures and diversity management related laws such as the implementation of the federal character principle will be undertaken with a view to ensuring greater promotion of merit for sustainable development in Nigeria.

According to The Transformation Agenda (2011-2015), Nigeria's inability to attain sustainable development in the past has been attributed to the nation's inability to tackle development challenges such as poverty, unemployment, corruption and security hinged on bad governance and ineffective institutions/agencies of government. The poor implementation of the principle of federal character in the Nigerian public service is therefore capable of bringing into the service incompetent workforce that lacks the ability to implement the policies of government for sustainable development. Gberevbie (2010) however argued that predicating employee recruitment on federal character does not mean that such an employee cannot contribute meaningfully towards the enhancement of the goals of the organization. This is particularly so where appropriate recruitment strategies involving the screening of potential employees based on relevant skills, experience and educational qualifications are adopted. What is important therefore is the ability of the individual employed and his/her willingness to work for the organization. In addition, through proper staff training and development by organizations of their workforce, organizational productivity is enhanced even where incompetent employees would have been employed through inappropriate recruitment strategies.

In the same vein, Olaopa (2012) commends the federal character principle as one of the "effective nation-building strategies invented for managing the combustible diversity in Nigeria." He however argues that "this principle has badly eroded professional and competency capacity of the public service." With this state of affairs, how can Nigeria attain sustainable development? Olaopa (2012) responded to this poser

by alluding to the declining content of the nation's tertiary education without the right skill to fill in the capacity gap in the public service. He concluded that "the nation unfortunately, could also no longer benefit from a "town and gown" networking that harnesses and deploys the full weight of the available academic capital and capacities to the task of national development" (Olaopa, 2012). In this regard, the application of the FC principle has failed to offer credible solutions to administrative ineffectiveness in the Nigerian public service and has actually become a drag on sustainable development. The implication of the foregoing is that unethical behavior among public officials and low productivity in the Nigerian public service can be explained by the appointment of incompetent personnel through the application the FC principle that makes it possible for people from the different segments of the society to be represented in government without due consideration for merit and quality training to enhance productivity.

Poor performance of officials in the Nigerian public service

One of the manifestations of the implementation of the federal character principle is the poor employee procurement practice, which results in unethical behaviour among public sector workers in Nigeria. Below are some of the instances: The audit investigation ordered by the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Petroleum Resources towards the end of 2011, with the involvement of Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), and was carried out by an internationally recognized audit firm- KPMG, revealed that the cost of subsidy payment on petroleum products not consumed by end users due to losses from theft and even those not supplied for use in Nigeria between 2007 and 2009 amounted to NGN11.8 billion or USD76.13million (Agbo,2012).

In the month of March 2012, the Nigerian Senate set up an Ad hoc Committee to investigate unethical behaviour amongst

public officials in the Nigerian Police Pension Fund Administration. While testifying on the pension fund management to the Senate Adhoc Committee, the former Head of Service of the Nigerian Civil Service and Chairman of the Nigerian Public Service Reform Committee of 2012, Stephen Oronsaye revealed that “top government officials were known to have falsified documents in order to siphon money from the pension fund” (Onwukwe, 2012). He disclosed that during his tenure as Head of the Nigerian Civil Service, it was discovered that the fraud was perpetrated from the office of the Accountant General of the Federation. According to him, "The Federal Government of Nigeria spent NGN5 billion or USD32.26 million monthly as pension when in the actual sense, pension expenses ought to be NGN1 billion or USD6.5 million only” (Onwukwe, 2012).

Furthermore, the Director, Pension Administration in the Office of the Head of Service, Dr. Sani Shuaibu and 31 other top officials were arrested by the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) for theft of NGN4.5 billion or USD29.03 million belonging to the Nigerian Police Pension Fund (Abuh, & Musari, 2012; Adewole, 2012). The Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) is a governmental agency established to oversee all port matters in Nigeria as it relates to international trade. However, appointment of public officials based on federal character principle/political patronage led to the appointment of Chief Bode George, a former National Vice-Chairman (West) of the ruling party in Nigeria- People's Democratic Party (PDP) as Chairman, board of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) in 2009. Chief Bode George and four other board members were charged by the EFCC before a Lagos High Court and were eventually jailed for contract inflation and mismanagement of NGN100 billion or USD645.16 million belonging to the NPA (Fanoro, 2012). This is a case of unethical behaviour amongst public officials to rob the nation of the benefits of international trade

and development. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2022) posit that “morality is the health of a society, and a society plagued with immorality is a sick society”. It is unfortunate that the funds that would have gone into developmental drive of the government are being mismanaged by incompetent workforce arising from the application of federal character principle in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study was centered on the theory of Liberalism by John Locke, which emphasizes on equal rights, individual freedom and equal opportunities for all citizens. Thus, the Nigerian public service must operate as an entity promoting equality and fairness at all times. Every citizen must therefore enjoy fair treatment despite their status or tribe, the opportunities in the decision making, appointment or recruitment must not be equally distributed to enhance development and peace. This condition or situation is what the federal character principle is trying to address (equity and fairness to all parts or geographical divides of the country).

Summary

The study examines the challenges and impact of the federal character (FC) principle in Nigeria. It observed that the FC principle as practiced in Nigeria diverts emphasis from merit (based on hard work and achievement) to sharing privileges and benefits accruable from representative bureaucracy, it thus limits effectiveness in public bureaucracy and ultimately national development. The application of FC principle runs counters some features of the Weberian bureaucratic model of rationality in the procurement and promotion of employees as cardinal planks upon which formal organizations should be built. This state of affairs impacts on administrative effectiveness and the expected

role of public bureaucracies in policy implementation for sustainable development.

The study observes that the practice of the Federal Character principle in Nigeria suffers from a major contradiction, because it brings about division amongst Nigerians rather than foster unity as was originally intended by its proponents as a policy option for managing the challenge of equal representation of people from different parts of the society in a multi-ethnic state like Nigeria. It submitted that where appropriate recruitment strategies involving the screening of potential employees based on relevant skills, experience and educational qualifications are adopted and the proper staff training and development of the workforce, organizational productivity could be enhanced even where incompetent employees would have been employed through (in some instances), the poor application of federal character principle in the Nigerian public service.

Finally, it was discovered that despite the efforts of the government to ensure equity and fairness, federal character principle has not achieved the desired results due to poor implementation in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The federal character principle, aimed at promoting national unity and balancing, has faced challenges in its implementation, leading to inefficiencies in the public sector. The study concludes that there is a need for restructuring of federalism in Nigeria, prioritizing merit in recruitment and promotion, and emphasizing human capacity and institutional development. It also concludes that building national consciousness and fundamentally changing the nature and character of leading elites and policy products are also crucial for effective public sector management. Based on this conclusion, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Federal government should prioritize merit in recruitment and promotion, ensuring geo-political balancing without compromising competence, to enhance the effectiveness of the public sector.
2. The Nigerian public sector should emphasize human capacity and institutional development, and promote good governance devoid of sentiments and unethical behaviour, to improve service delivery and performance.
3. Policy makers should fundamentally change the nature and character of leadership and policy products, shifting from particularistic tendencies and interests to a more nationalistic and inclusive approach, to drive development and national unity.

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THE GROWING AWARENESS OF THE ROLES OF COMMUNITY POLICING IN ESAN LAND, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

Aziegbemhin S. IKHAYERE, Ph.D

Department of Public Administration

College of Management and Social Sciences (COLMASS)

Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

ikhayereaz@gmail.com

08053330493; 08035746112

Abstract

This study empirically examined the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria. It specifically aimed at investigating the extent of awareness of community policing in Esan land. To achieve this, an online survey method of investigation was applied as well as structured questionnaire were distributed in the major communities in Esan West Local Government Area, of Edo State. A sample size of 201 respondents was carefully selected through random sampling techniques. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) was used for all the analyses. All tests were carried out at the 5% level of statistical significance. The findings revealed that greater number of respondents are aware of community policing in their locality. It also revealed that there is a significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in sensitization of crime prevention. It recommended that there is need to improve management practices in community policing; and the changes management required